

PHYTOFLORA AND BIODIVERSITY OF ALGAE IN THE WATER BODIES OF SALYAN DISTRICT

MASUME RAMAZAN QIZI BAGIROVA

Master's

Baku State University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Ph.D. in Biology, Associate Professor **SHAKAR JALAL QIZI MUKHTAROVA**

The main relief of Azerbaijan, the Kura-Aras lowland, is located in the southeastern part of the country and covers a vast area [2]. This lowland consists of alluvial plains formed by the Kura and Aras rivers and is characterized by a semi-desert and dry steppe climate zone. Significant scientific works have been carried out on algae in the Kura-Aras lowland, especially the ecological and taxonomic characteristics of diatom algae, which were extensively analyzed by S.K. Jafarova and Sh.J. Mukhtarova [1]. Besides that, other studies related to the algal flora of the lowland also exist [3], [4], [5].

Picture 1. The location of Salyan District on the map of the Republic of Azerbaijan

Salyan district is located in the southeastern part of the Kura-Aras lowland. The relief of the district is mainly flat, and its climate is characterized by semi-desert and dry steppe zones. The Kura River and its artificial canals are present here. Anthropogenic impacts especially the discharge of fertilizers and household waste affect the ecological condition of the water bodies.

Algae (phytoplankton) are one of the main biocomponents of these aquatic ecosystems. They provide primary production of organic matter through photosynthesis, participate in oxygen production, and are considered key organisms determining the trophic level of the water. The species diversity, quantity, and distribution characteristics of algal flora serve as natural bioindicators reflecting the ecological condition of the ecosystem.

The algal flora of Salyan district has not yet been fully studied. In this regard, the aim of our research is to investigate the species composition and biodiversity of algae in the natural and artificial water bodies of Salyan district and to determine their relationship with ecological conditions. The obtained results will contribute to ecological monitoring of the region and sustainable management of water resources.

The research was conducted during the spring and summer of 2025 by collecting 24 water samples from 7 different water bodies in Salyan district. From each water body, a 100 ml water sample was collected. Samples were taken in sterile glass containers and analyzed microscopically in the laboratory. Identification of algae was carried out based on morphological features and recognized taxonomic keys [7], [8], [9]. The physical-chemical parameters of water temperature and pH were measured.

The lakes and reservoirs of Salyan district hold strategic importance in the southern region of Azerbaijan for the conservation of biological diversity and the maintenance of ecosystem stability. According to the results, the biodiversity of algae in the water bodies of Salyan district, located in the southeastern Kura-Aras lowland, is rich. Studies showed that green algae (Chlorophyta) were dominant in most samples and were observed in stagnant and nutrient-rich waters. The second most abundant were blue-green algae (Cyanobacteria), mainly found in stagnant and pollution-prone waters. Diatom algae (Bacillariophyta) ranked third. These microorganisms play an important role as bioindicators of water quality [6].

Results showed that the species composition of algae in Salyan district's water bodies is closely related to water mobility, light levels, and anthropogenic impacts. The study indicates that the main threat to the water bodies of Salyan district comes from agricultural activities, specifically fertilizer and pesticide runoff. Therefore, sustainable management of water resources, protection of the natural environment, and strengthening biomonitoring measures are crucial. The obtained results serve not only for Salyan district but also provide a scientific basis for ecological planning and biodiversity conservation strategies in the entire Kura-Aras lowland.

These results can be used as a fundamental database for biomonitoring of aquatic environments.

- This research provides a scientific foundation for decision-making related to water ecology and biodiversity conservation in the region.
- Strengthening control over the discharge of fertilizers and household waste during water body management is essential.
- Biomonitoring programs should be established to ensure temporal and spatial monitoring of algal flora in water bodies.

The results of this work can be used as an advisory mechanism in high schools, universities, and ecological management agencies.

REFERENCES

1. Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences Central Botanical Garden Scientific Works, Volume VIII, 2011.
2. Barinova S.S., Medvedeva L.A. (1996). Atlas of Algae – Indicators of Saprobity (Russian Far East). Vladivostok: Dalnauka, 364 p.
3. Jafarova S.K., Sh.J. Mukhtarova. Diatom Algae of Azerbaijan's Freshwaters (checklist, synonyms, ecology, and distribution). Baku: "Elm", 2018.
4. Karaeva N.I., Mukhtarova Sh.J. (1987). Rare and New Species of Pennate Diatoms (Bacillariophyta) of Azerbaijan for the USSR. Botanical Journal, Vol. 72, No. 7: 943-948.
5. Mukhtarova Sh.J. (2000). Materials on the Algoflora of Water Bodies on the Southern Slopes of the Greater Caucasus. Proceedings of the Scientific Conference on "Modern Problems of Biology". Baku State University, Baku.
6. Museibov M.A. Physical Geography of Azerbaijan. Baku, 1998.
7. www.algaebase.org
8. www.calacademy.org
9. www.algaterria.org